

Cationic Polymerisation of *N*-Vinylcarbazole by some (3d) Transition Metal Ion loaded 13X Molecular Sieves

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The polymerisation of *N*-vinylcarbazole by 13X molecular sieves modified by five different transition metal ions, namely, Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} has been studied at a fixed metal ion incorporation. The order of reactivity follows the trend, $Mn^{II} \approx Cu^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II}$. The energy of activation has been found to decrease with decrease in pH of the exchange solution in every system. Molecular weights are characteristically high in the present system with a molecular weight distribution >3 . The observed characteristics of the polymerisation have been explained in terms of a dual initiation mechanism involving (i) transition metal ion centre and (ii) proton sites which are generated during metal ion exchange process.

MOLECULAR sieve catalysts are characterised by high activity and selectivity in a wide variety of organic reactions including polymerisation. Biswas and Maity¹ have reviewed the present status of research involving molecular sieves as polymerisation catalysts. The structural and compositional characteristics of various sieves, such as 3Å, 4Å, 5Å, 10X and 13X and the rare earth exchanged zeolites, like SK-500 qualify their specificity in initiating cationic polymerisation of vinyl monomers.

13X molecular sieves reportedly induce the high molecular weight cationic polymerisation of styrene². H-mordenite and H-faujasite (H-Y) polymerise ethyl vinyl, *n*-butyl vinyl and isobutyl vinyl ethers to low molecular weight polymers^{3,4}. Biswas and Maity^{5,6} observed fast polymerisation of *N*-vinylcarbazole (NVC) and isobutyl vinyl ether by SK-500, a rare earth exchanged molecular sieve. In general, 13X molecular sieves exhibit poorer initiating capacity compared to SK-500. This implies that the enhanced activity of SK-500 may arise from the presence of rare earth metal ions. It may hence be expected that the cationic reactivity of 13X may perhaps be enhanced by incorporation of transition metal ions in the network of 13X. Initial experiments by Biswas *et al.*^{7,8} with Cu^{II} and Co^{II} exchanged 13X molecular sieves confirmed these expectations in NVC polymerisation. In addition, these studies also revealed the role of H^+ concentration of the exchanging metal salt solution in the initiation process and highlighted the importance of double initiation centres in the metal-ion exchanged 13X zeolites.

In this article, the polymerisation initiating activities of Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} exchanged 13X molecular sieves in NVC polymerisation have been

described. The results are significant in that they establish the relative efficiencies of the various 3d metal ions in enhancing the initiating activity of 13X. Also, they endorse the general validity of the double initiation mechanism⁹ in these polymerisation.

Experimental

NVC (BASF, West Germany) was recrystallised from methanol by the standard procedure⁷. $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (E. Merck, G.R.) were used as such. Linde 13X (Union Carbide, U.S.A.) was supplied as a white powder containing no clay binder. All solvents (A.R.) were purified and fractionated by standard methods.

Preparation of metal solution and pH measurement: Exactly 0.2 M solutions of manganese(II) chloride, nickel(II) chloride and zinc(II) sulphate were prepared. The pH of the solutions was varied by the addition of an aqueous protonic acid containing the same anion as that of the corresponding metal salt and was measured by a digital pH meter at 35°.

Metal exchange method: The exchange of sodium ions in 13X zeolite by manganese(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) ions was performed by stirring the 13X zeolites in 0.2 M solutions of the respective salts at 35°. The same exchange level (30% in each case) was maintained by appropriate experimental manipulations and was estimated by standard analysis of the metal ions. After the final exchange, the material was collected by filtration, washed free of the corresponding anions, heated to 100° for 2 h, cooled to room temperature in a dry-box, and powdered to 100 mesh size. The

catalyst was activated at 500° for 2 h before each experiment.

Polymerisation : All polymerisations were conducted in Pyrex vessels (50 ml capacity) in a nitrogen atmosphere under constant stirring. All experimental manipulations, including charging reaction vessels with solvents (toluene), monomer and catalysts were performed in a dry glove-box⁹. The catalyst after activation (500° for 2 h) was transferred to the monomer solution under nitrogen atmosphere. The progress of the polymerisation was followed gravimetrically.

Molecular weight : The molecular weight of the polymers was determined viscometrically with a Ubbelohde viscometer using the equation¹⁰,

$$[\eta] = 76.2 \times 10^{-5} [M]^{0.50} \text{ (solvent toluene at } 35^\circ\text{)}$$

Gel permeation chromatography : In a few cases the molecular weight and molecular weight distribution of the polymers were measured on a Toyo Soda GPC instrument using THF as solvent with a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹ at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

Nature of polymerisation and general order of reactivity : The polymerisation of NVC with different 3d transition metal ion-loaded 13X proceeds with no induction period at 40° upwards. It has been established^{6,11} through the decelerating influence of pyridine and water on the rate and molecular weight that the polymerisation of NVC by metal ion-loaded 13X proceeds by a cationic mechanism. The polymerisations are not accompanied by any colour change¹² suggesting that charge transfer initiation through interaction of metal ions with the =N lone pair of NVC is unimportant.

Rate and molecular weight data for the polymerisation of NVC with different 3d transition metal ion-loaded 13X are summarised in Table 1. As revealed by these data, the efficiency of the different metal ions in the initiation of NVC polymerisation follows the trend,

The highest initiating activity of Mn^{II} is consistent with the earlier available reports^{13,14} on the catalytic influence of manganese ions on vinyl polymerisation. The trend observed in the present context possibly reflects the combined influence of factors, such as electronegativity, ionic radius and coordination number of the concerned metal ions on the initiation process. Metal ion electronegativity controls the polarisation of the π-electron cloud of the vinyl group, while the coordination number and ionic radius influence the accommodation and spatial arrangement of the monomer molecules coordinated to the metal ion in the 13X cage. Attempts are being made to understand more quantitatively the significance of the factors cited above in the present context.

TABLE 1—POLYMERISATION CHARACTERISTICS* OF NVC OVER METAL**-LOADED 13X MOLECULAR SIEVE CATALYST SYSTEMS

Exchanging metal ion	Temp. °C	R _p × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	M̄ _v ^a
Cu ^{II}	60	33.90	36 900
	50	25.70	
	40	15.80	
Co ^{II}	60	23.00	37 670
	50	17.00	
	40	12.05	
Ni ^{II}	60	9.12	36 820 ^b
	50	6.16	
	40	3.98	
Mn ^{II}	60	32.36	48 380
	50	25.70	
	40	19.02	
Zn ^{II}	60	15.20	26 500
	50	11.75	
	40	9.12	

* 0.15 mol dm⁻³ of NVC in toluene and 25 g dm⁻³ of catalyst used in each reaction. ** 30% of metal exchanged in each case.

^aViscosity average molecular weight. ^bMolecular weight obtained from GPC curve.

Dual initiation mechanism : Biswas *et al.*^{7,8} conclusively proved for both Cu^{II} and Co^{II} loaded 13X-NVC polymerisation systems that the variation of the initiating activities at the same level of metal ion-loading is primarily due to the difference in the pH of the exchange salt solution. The latter is considered to effect varying degrees of proton-exchange with the zeolite during the metal ion-exchange process. These proton centres therefore also participate in the initiation mechanism. Schematically, a generalised polymerisation initiation mechanism in the light of these considerations should include the essential steps as under

Initiation :

where, M is monomer, LC and LH are respectively metal cation site and proton cation site on zeolite, M₁ is adsorbed M on metal cation site, MH is adsorbed M on proton site, k_{1c} and k_{1h} are rate constant for initiation on metal ion site and protonic site, respectively S is solvent and S₁ is adsorbed S on metal cation site.

Fig. 1 shows that in all the systems studied in the present context, R_p vs H⁺ concentration (of the exchange solution) plots at a fixed exchange level

of metal ion give a smooth straight line which leaves an intercept at a hypothetical zero surface proton concentration. Apparently, the intercept corresponds to the rate due to metal ion initiation alone.

Fig. 1. The variation of R_p with $[H^+]$ of exchanging salt solution in the polymerisation of NVC at 60° ; $[NVC] = 0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Catalyst] = 25 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, and exchange level = 30%.

Activation energy data : Table 2 summarises the activation energy data calculated from the usual Arrhenius plot of R_p vs $1/T$ in the temperature range 40 - 60° . Interestingly, the activation energies are

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF ENERGY OF ACTIVATION ON pH OF EXCHANGE METAL SOLUTION IN NVC-METAL EXCHANGED* 13X POLYMERISATION SYSTEM**

Exchanging metal ion	pH of exchanging solution ^a	Energy of activation ^b kJ mol^{-1}
Mn^{II}	3.52	23.95
	3.97	26.63
	4.72	28.01
	5.61	30.20
Co^{II}	3.65	28.30
	3.90	33.77
	4.98	36.41
Ni^{II}	3.52	37.29
	3.56	33.27
Cu^{II}	3.89	38.50
	4.30	45.85
	5.39	51.33
Zn^{II}	3.54	24.20
	3.95	26.17
	4.61	29.00
	5.10	33.57

* 30% of metal exchanged in each case. ** 0.15 mol dm^{-3} of NVC in toluene and 25 g dm^{-3} of catalyst used in each reaction.

^a 0.2 M solution, 35° . ^b Measured from Arrhenius plots.

distinctly influenced by pH of the salt solution confirming that the overall rate of polymerisation is actually a composite function⁷,

$$R_p = R_p^0 + R_p^H \\ = R_p^0 + k_H [H^+]$$

where, R_p^0 is rate due to metal cation and k_H is composite rate constant accommodating the monomer and metal ion concentration.

Molecular weight trend : A notable feature of the molecular weights of these polymerisations is their relatively high values compared with those realised with other NVC polymerisation systems including even the polymerisation by SK-500^{5,6}. Thus, it is gratifying to note that modification of 13X by metal ion loading makes it possible to realise higher molecular weights, which is in fact, one of the major objectives of this research.

Molecular weight distribution : A few typical molecular weight distribution curves are known in Fig. 2. The dispersities ($\overline{M}_w/\overline{M}_n$) of the polymers are rather high (> 3) indicating an 'unclean' polymerisation system, due possibly to the simultaneous presence of proton-initiated and metal ion-initiated polymers as speculated in dual initiation mechanism. In fact, the GPC traces reveal shoulders indicating some bimodal nature of the molecular weight distribution; which is in line with the above contention. It is relevant to recall at this stage that Barson *et al.*⁹ reported relatively narrower distribution (1.5) for the polymerisation of styrene by 13X zeolite. Low values of dispersion are usually associated with

Fig. 2. Molecular weight distribution curves of poly(NVC) obtained from NVC- Co^{II} -13X system; $[NVC] = 0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Catalyst] = 25 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, exchange level of $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} = 30\%$ and reaction temperature = 60° : (a) $\text{pH} = 3.90$ and (b) $\text{pH} = 3.65$.

reactions having rapid initiation and no termination or transfer. Judging in light of this general notion, the relatively broad distribution implies a relatively

different initiating and propagating activities of the two polymerisation centres and also the existence of a predominantly termination/transfer controlled polymerisation system.

Conclusion :

The modification of 13X molecular sieves by several 3d transition metal ions influences their activity to varying extents in regard to the cationic polymerisation of NVC. Initiation in this system occurs by (i) the involvement of metal ion centres and (ii) protons occurring during metal ion exchange. The molecular weights of the poly(NVC) thus obtained are higher than those reported with conventional catalyst systems. The dispersities of the poly(NVC) are also > 3 in a few cases studied.

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